

Publisher: Scientific-Professional Society for Disaster Risk Management

International Journal of Disaster Risk Management

Evaluating Puntland's Disaster Risk Management Policy: Institutional Preparedness, Community Engagement and Implementation Challenges

Mohamed Musse Mohamed Kalakaan^{1,2*}

¹ Institute for Studies, Researchers and Academic Community [ISRAAC], Puntland, Somalia; mohamed.muse@uobg.edu.so.

² Faculty of Social Science, University of Bosaso Garowe, Puntland, Somalia.

* Correspondence: mmkalakaan@gmail.com/Mohamed.muse@uobg.edu.so; Tel.: +252-907-774-2228

Received: 1 May 2025; Revised: 15 June 2025; Accepted: 18 June 2025; Published: 30 June 2025.

ABSTRACT

Disaster Risk Management (DRM) plays a pivotal role in governance, particularly in regions prone to recurrent hazards, such as Puntland and Somalia. This study critically examines the effectiveness of Puntland's 2014 Disaster Risk Management (DRM) Policy, with a focus on disaster preparedness, institutional coordination, and community engagement. Using a qualitative case study approach that includes key informant interviews, focus group discussions, and document analysis, it assesses whether the policy remains relevant in mitigating disaster risks, aligns with global frameworks, and integrates effectively into Puntland's governance system. The study applies the OECD policy evaluation framework and compares Puntland's DRM approach against global and national benchmarks, including the Sendai Framework and Somalia's 2020 National Disaster Risk Management (DRM) Policy. Findings indicate significant policy gaps, including weak institutional coordination, inadequate financial resources, and minimal public engagement in disaster response efforts, which fail to empower local governments. A case study of the Qardho district illustrates the real-world impact of these shortcomings, particularly in response delays and ineffective recovery strategies. The study emphasises the need for a comprehensive policy revision that enhances institutional capacity, defines clear stakeholder responsibilities, ensures sustainable funding, and promotes meaningful community involvement. Aligning Puntland's DRM strategy with the Sendai Framework for Disaster Risk Reduction, Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), and Somalia's National DRM Policy (2020) can strengthen regional resilience and adaptive capacity. By addressing these deficiencies, Puntland can establish a more effective, inclusive DRM framework that safeguards vulnerable communities and mitigates disaster risks.

KEYWORDS

Disaster risk management; public policy; institutional preparedness; Puntland; community engagement.

Copyright: © 2024 by the authors.

Mohamed Kalakaan, M. M. (2025). Evaluating Puntland's Disaster Risk Management Policy: Institutional Preparedness, Community Engagement and Implementation Challenges. *International Journal of Disaster Risk Management*, 7(1), 507–518.

1. Introduction

Disasters pose a growing threat to human security, economic stability, and infrastructure development, particularly in vulnerable regions like Puntland and Somalia. The frequency and intensity of natural disasters—ranging from droughts and floods to tropical cyclones—have increased over the past three decades, exacerbating socio-economic challenges and disrupting development efforts (UNDP, 2022). The government must seek relief or reduce disaster risks through systematic efforts to analyse and manage the factors that interact with hazards to cause disasters (United Nations International Strategy for Disaster Reduction [UNISDR], 2009). Otherwise, the impacts of disaster can disrupt the progress and developmental efforts of nations, often pushing them many years back (Smith & Matthews, 2015). Puntland's 2014 Disaster Risk Management (DRM) Policy was developed to provide a structured response to disasters, yet challenges persist in its implementation. Because many policies remain theoretical frameworks rather than practical solutions, particularly in fragile states like Somalia (Ji & Lee, 2021). Policy-making is a multifaceted discipline and activity that cannot be adequately considered apart from the environment, the local community, its leadership, and even the stakeholders in which it takes place because the essence of public policy lies in society (Juma, 2015). Disaster management refers to the body of policy and administrative decisions, operational activities, actors, and technologies that pertain to the various stages of a disaster at all levels (Suriant et al., 2019; Cvetkovic et al., 2021, 2025).

This study evaluates whether the 2014 DRM policy remains relevant and responsive to current disaster management needs. This research assesses whether the policy's formulation was sufficiently inclusive and comprehensive. Are Puntland's government agencies institutionally prepared to implement it effectively? To address these questions and gather relevant insights, this paper critically reviews the 2014 DRM Policy, focusing on three key aspects: (1) Institutional Preparedness – How well are Puntland's government agencies equipped to implement DRM strategies? (2) Community Engagement – To what extent are local communities involved in disaster response and mitigation? (3) Implementation Challenges – What structural and financial barriers hinder the effective implementation of DRM policies? By evaluating the policy's effectiveness, this study aims to identify practical recommendations for strengthening disaster governance in Puntland, ensuring that DRM strategies are translated into actionable frameworks that benefit at-risk communities (UNDP, 2022).

2. DRM Policy in the State of Puntland, Somalia

The governance system of Somalia, as adopted in 2004, is characterised by a federal structure comprising three distinct layers: the federal government, state governments, and local governments. Each of these entities operates within semi-autonomous institutional frameworks and is constitutionally mandated to address the needs and demands of citizens within their respective jurisdictions, delivering services in a holistic and accountable manner. The State of Puntland, established in 1998—six years before Somalia adopted the federal system—has functioned as a semi-autonomous government within the broader federal system of the Republic of Somalia. Puntland is geographically located in the northeastern part of Somalia and occupies a total land area of 212,510 square kilometres, or roughly one-third of Somalia's geographical area. It is a semi-arid region with a warm climate, characterised by average daily temperatures ranging from 270 °C to 370 °C.

The State of Puntland shares many similarities with Somalia, and disasters can manifest in various forms, including delayed rain, floods, droughts, epidemics, and tropical cyclones, with droughts occurring more frequently. The major drought incidents remembered since 1990 include Jiqiiqan of 1990/2, Jihajihays of 1994, Naafmadoobe and Naafcadda of 1996/7, Haruure and Kartoomaley of 2001 and 2004, Ari War Maleh of 2008, Erdogan of 2011, Hawdaad of 2014, and Sima of 2016. Additionally, Puntland experienced the Tsunami disaster in 2004, which affected the coastal communities between the island of Hafun in the Bari region and the village of Garacad in Mudug, a 650-kilometre stretch of coastline, and killed at least 114 people, destroyed 100 fishing boats and the villages in the area have been either fully or partially submerged (The Office for the Coordination of Humanitarian Affairs (OCHA, 2004).

To address the hazards of Tsunamis, Puntland established the Humanitarian Affairs and Disaster Management Agency (HADMA) in 2005, operating under the leadership of Puntland's Ministry of Interior, Federal Affairs, and Democratisation. HADMA drafted a Disaster Risk Management policy in 2014, which was subsequently approved by the cabinet. This DRM Policy explicitly outlines the dos and don'ts of the Puntland government and adopts a regulatory-focused approach to disaster management and mitigation.

In 2022, HADMA was elevated into the Ministry of Humanitarian Affairs and Disaster Management (MoHADM) with presidential decree number 25 on April 18, 2022, mandating the coordination and leading distribution of humanitarian aid, developing and implementing policies, strategies and programmes related to humanitarian aid and disaster management, advocacy and Awareness activities and upholding the principles of accountability, transparency and inclusivity in all humanitarian and disaster management programmes and projects in Puntland. Due to recurrent hazards, Puntland recognised the need for the establishment of the Puntland Disaster Risk Management Policy, formulated in December 2014, which aims to provide a structured approach to disaster risk management (DRM) by addressing preparedness, mitigation, response, and recovery. The policy focuses on reducing the impact of disasters, both natural and human-induced, such as droughts, floods, and epidemics. It outlines the roles and responsibilities of various stakeholders, including the Puntland Disaster Management Council, HADMA, local governments, and international partners. According to the 2014 DRM Policy, the key aspects of the policy include (1) establishing HADMA under the Office of the President to oversee disaster management activities and ensure coordination among stakeholders, (2) Proposing financial mechanisms such as disaster management funds (3) Emphasizing the integration of disaster risk management into development planning, enhancing community resilience, and safeguarding critical infrastructure, (4) Highlighting the importance of training, public awareness, and integrating disaster risk reduction into educational curricula, and (5) Recognizing the specific needs of women and vulnerable groups in disaster preparedness and response.

3. Methods

This study employed a qualitative case design to assess Puntland's 2014 Disaster Risk Management (DRM) policy. This approach was chosen for its ability to generate in-depth insights into institutional dynamics and stakeholder perspectives within complex governance contexts (Gautam & Phaiju, 2013). Data was collected through three primary sources: document analysis, key informant interviews (KIIs), and focus group discussions (FGDs). The document review included the 2014 Puntland DRM policy, the 2020 National DRM Policy of the Federal Republic of Somalia, the DRM Strategic Plan developed by MoHADM, as well as the DRM Strategic plans of selected districts, Garowe and Qardho.

Primary data collection consisted of twelve focus group discussions (FGDs) conducted in the Garowe and Qardho districts, with each group comprising 8 to 11 participants, totalling 120 individuals. Participants were drawn from local governments' DRM units, disaster management-related ministries, Associations for Local Governments of Puntland [ALGAPL], NGOs, civil society organisations, academic institutions, and community groups, including representatives of vulnerable groups. In parallel, five Key Informant Interviews (KIIs) were conducted with senior officials from key ministries, including the Ministry of Health, Administration and Development Management (MoHADM), the Ministry of Environment, Range and Climate Change, the Ministry of Education and Higher Education, as well as the mayor of Qardho district. Qardho was selected as a focal case study due to its repeated exposure to flooding and its significance as a testing ground for the effectiveness of disaster risk management (DRM) policies in real-life emergency contexts. This helped to assess the practical aspects of institutional preparedness and community involvement during real emergencies. It also utilised secondary sources, such as academic papers, reviews, and related policy documents, specifically the DRM policy of the Federal Republic of Somalia, as the country's political system is federal with a tripartite government.

To analyse the findings, this study applied the OECD Policy Evaluation Framework, which examines six key dimensions (OECD, 2020), namely relevance – does the policy address Puntland’s current disaster risks? Effectiveness – has the policy reduced disaster impacts in Puntland since 2014? Efficiency – are financial and institutional resources allocated efficiently? Coherence – how well does the policy align with Somalia’s national DRM strategy and international frameworks? Impact – What measurable improvements in disaster preparedness have resulted from the policy? Moreover, sustainability – does the policy provide long-term solutions, particularly in financial and institutional capacities? The study also employed a conceptual differentiation of public policy; in the analysis of policy, the word policy is differentiated into three dimensions: ‘polity’, which refers to political institutions and the political system, ‘politics’ in the processual dimension, that is, the political process, and ‘policy’ which refers to public policies per se (Greece, et al., 2014). The analysis of Policy is concerned with the process of constructing public policy, focusing on the definition of the agenda and highlighting aspects such as the interests of actors participating in the political game, as well as the interaction between them (Serafim & Dias, 2012). Together, these frameworks enabled a multidimensional analysis of the DRM policy, linking theoretical constructs to empirical findings and providing a comprehensive view of its governance, implementation, and institutional effectiveness.

4. Results and Discussion

Based on the review of the 2014 Disaster Risk Management (DRM) Policy document of Puntland, the study highlighted significant gaps within the policy framework. After rigorous analysis, this section presents the study’s findings:

4.1. Policy Alignment and Strategic Relevance

After rigorous analysis, the study found that Puntland’s DRM policy (2014) lacks standardisation of the policy in alignment with the current international frameworks like the Sendai Framework for Disaster Risk Reduction (2015-2030), the African Union Agenda 2063, Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs 2015- 2030), Paris Agreement on Climate Change of 2020, and among others. Despite the policy states frameworks such as the Hyogo Framework for Action (2005-2015), it also outlines a broad framework for disaster management. However, it lacks detailed, hazard-specific strategies for disasters like droughts, floods, or epidemics. Likewise, the SIDRA report highlights that the 2014 policy lacks alignment with contemporary international frameworks for disaster risk management and demonstrates inadequate integration with the local ones (Somalia Institute for Development and Research Analysis [SIDRA], 2020).

The study further revealed that the 2014 Disaster Risk Management (DRM) Policy lacks alignment with other national legal frameworks related to DRM and demonstrates limited integration of disaster management across key sectoral public policies, including environmental protection, urban planning, and public health. Moreover, the policy does not acknowledge several hazards identified in the Federal Republic of Somalia’s National DRM Policy (2020), such as tropical cyclones, storm surges, entomological and pest outbreaks, fire incidents, conflict and terrorism, as well as hazardous materials including marine oil spills, waste spills, and plastic pollution.

Subsequently, the 2014 Disaster Risk Management (DRM) policy does not classify conflict or terrorism as disasters, despite the war on terror and border conflicts being key strategic priorities in Puntland’s government agenda. Whenever such conflicts arise, Puntland enters a state of emergency. For example, the 2011 war against Al-Shabaab in the Galgala Mountains, the 2016 Suuj-Garmaal war against Al-Shabaab, and the ongoing large-scale battle against ISIS/Da’ish in the Almaskat mountains, which involves international terrorist fighters pose a significant security threat. Additionally, Puntland has experienced multiple border disputes, which have also led to emergency declarations due to their socio-political and economic impact. Given their severe consequences, these conflicts can be considered disasters and warrant inclusion in the Disaster Risk Management (DRM)

framework. Should the government not formally recognise it as a disaster or significant threat when acts of terrorists or wars result in widespread harm and disruption?

In brief, the lack of coordination between Puntland's DRM policy and Somalia's federal disaster response mechanisms may also lead to challenges in resource sharing, policy implementation, and coordinated responses.

4.2. Institutional Coordination and Governance

In the context of DRM, the most important set of actors are government and local institutions. They play a vital role as both the primary implementers of policies and frontline responders during emergencies. "Local governments are fully responsible for the safety of their citizens and communities (Suriyanto et al., 2019)." Their responsibilities involve not only executing disaster management strategies but also ensuring the immediate safety and well-being of affected communities. Since they are considered the most closely connected governmental entity to local people. The local government has a direct connection with the community people to establish proactive disaster management (Kafle, 2018).

Thus, the question arises: What are the implications if such a significant institution within the government structure has its pivotal role in DRM undermined? Although the 2014 DRM policy emphasises the importance of collaboration, it appears to fail to clearly define the roles and responsibilities within the DRM governance arrangement. It does not explicitly assign roles to local governments. It does not provide precise mechanisms to prevent duplication of efforts among agencies. According to the respondents, the roles and responsibilities of local authorities are neither articulated in the policy nor were they consulted during its formulation.

Furthermore, the KIIs conducted with senior officials from local authorities revealed that they were unaware of the DRM policy's existence. This lack of awareness and practical application suggests that the policy remains largely a theoretical document with minimal on-the-ground impact. The 2014 DRM policy also failed to promote the decentralisation of essential disaster risk management tasks to local governments. These tasks include mapping and supervising high-risk areas, educating the public about potential hazards, and implementing land-use management to mitigate risks, such as construction in flood-prone or landslide-prone areas and resource mobilisation. The respondent further noted that there is no dedicated department specifically for disaster management. According to Law No. 3 of 2023 of regions and local governments, "districts are authorised to have five operational departments: finance, revenue, planning and monitoring & evaluation, social affairs, and public works." However, disaster management is addressed only as a unit within the Social Affairs Department. According to the SIDRA report, local authorities face significant challenges in managing disaster risk due to the lack of dedicated disaster management departments at the district level (SIDRA, 2020).

Based on primary data collected through interviews and field research, this highlights an apparent lack of trust by the state government in the capacity of local governments to manage disaster-related projects, thereby undermining the crucial role that local governments could play in disaster preparedness, mitigation, and recovery. Furthermore, there is a notable scarcity of professional public policy drafters, which is compounded by limited funding to hire qualified and resourceful experts (Ministry of Planning, Economic Development, and International Cooperation [MoPIC], 2020).

The second iteration of this policy should introduce new governance structures to streamline coordination among different stakeholders and build the capacity of DRM-related institutions, with clearly defined roles and responsibilities among government institutions to ensure the effective implementation of various policy actions. Otherwise, overlapping roles can lead to ineffectiveness, confusion, and resource wastage during emergencies. There must be a coordination platform under the Ministry of Humanitarian Affairs and Disaster Management in Puntland to streamline communication and clearly define roles for each stakeholder, particularly local governments. When dealing with DRM, local governments are required to serve as the implementing agent and frontline personnel. Disasters occur locally and require local-level approaches (Scot & Tarazona, 2011; Ainuddin et

al., 2013; Garschagen, 2016; Rumbach, 2015; Munene et al., 2016; Raikes et al., 2019; EDRMC, 2022). Policies and legislation related to risk management are crucial in defining the efficiency of on-the-ground implementation of the Disaster Management Plan (Suriyanto et al., 2019). Besides, train local government officials in disaster management through short courses and executive programmes (Ikram et al., 2020).

4.3. Financial Mechanisms and Sustainability

The 2014 Disaster Risk Management (DRM) policy proposed the establishment of a Puntland Disaster Management Fund, allocating 1% of the state-level annual budget, and a District Disaster Management Fund, derived from 2% of local taxation, to address disasters and emergencies. However, based on the key informant interviews with the MoHADM and mayoral district leadership, these initiatives have not been implemented because the proposed disaster funds rely heavily on external donations and limited government allocations, with no sustainable funding strategies in place. In this regard, the researcher posed a direct question to key policymakers at the ministerial and mayoral levels. Both parties emphasised that the proposed disaster management fund outlined in the policy document had not been established or operationalised.

Furthermore, no legislative framework had been written to administer the fund, nor had any financial resources been allocated to it. According to a SIDRA report, the policymakers clarified that no formal fund had been collected for disaster management, apart from contributions from NGOs and the community for recovery activities. Community contributions are initiated and managed by a group of trusted local sheikhs who operate independently of governmental oversight (SIDRA, 2020). The analysis highlights a significant gap between policy formulation and practical execution. The study revealed that limited financial resources remain a significant constraint, significantly undermining the government's capacity to craft attainable and actionable disaster risk management policies and strategies.

The study also proposes the establishment and operationalisation of the Puntland Disaster Management Fund (PDMF) and District Disaster Management Funds (DDMF), administered by highly prominent and trusted individuals, to ensure that sufficient financial resources are available for disaster preparedness and response. At this point, the government should formalise the role of sheikhs or other trusted community leaders by establishing a dedicated government agency responsible for managing local fund contributions and ensuring accountability and transparency. Additionally, to improve financial sustainability, Puntland should explore alternative financing models, for instance, Public-Private Partnerships (PPPs), which encourage private sector contributions in exchange for tax incentives (UNDP, 2022). Likewise, Balanggoy (2024) argues that "to explore collaborative alliances with private entities to secure financial support for training initiatives, projects, and various undertakings".

4.4. Community Engagement and Local Ownership

According to the analysis, this study observed that the 2014 DRM policy does not elaborate on mechanisms for engaging the community in planning and implementation. During the focus group discussions, most respondents identified the major factors hindering the effectiveness of DRM policy implementation at the local level as being attributed to the absence of local community participation. Limited community involvement can result in ineffective response measures and a lack of local ownership. The integrated community members share the same aim of reducing community-level hazards independently (Joerin, Shaw, Takeuchi, & Krishnamurthy, 2012). Similar results were found in the study by Balanggoy (2024), that "the ability to prevent, mitigate, and recover from disasters depends on people's and organisations' capacity, which is a part of disaster risk reduction and management (DRRM)". At the local level, there is the best knowledge about the characteristics of the local topography, available resources and living conditions. That is why local structures must be actively involved in the disaster management process in all phases, from development plans and

disaster response plans to addressing their consequences. Therefore, a bottom-up management approach is necessary in this sector to obtain a model that solves the problem at its source. (Đorđević & Gačić, 2024). Local communities play a pivotal role in strengthening the effectiveness of solidarity and cooperation within communities, facilitating individual efforts, building synergistic effects, and providing a platform for consensus-building and conflict avoidance, thereby building local social capital. Policy development and stakeholder engagement at international, regional, national, and sectoral levels determine whether awareness is raised, a common understanding emerges, norms develop, decisions are made, actions are promoted, and sustainability is ensured (Leka & Jain, 2014).

Similarly, other scholars like Milošević, Cvjetković-Ivetic, and Baturan (2024) argue that “previous studies have shown that public awareness campaigns and community-based programs play a vital role in disaster preparedness and recovery. By increasing efforts to educate citizens on their rights and responsibilities in the context of disaster recovery, the government can foster a culture of resilience and shared responsibility”. Therefore, strengthening communities, making responses more efficient, and encouraging a mindset of readiness that can all be achieved through organised training programs and seminars” (Balanggoy (2024).

In line with these findings, community engagement fosters a sense of ownership among local people, and thereby, they are more likely to trust their capacities, take collective action, and support one another in responding to disaster risks.

4.5. Case Analysis: Qardho Floods and Policy Gap

Developing countries are becoming increasingly vulnerable to disasters due to the combined effects of global warming and rapid urbanisation in high-risk areas (Ricardo, Pedro, & Lucas, 2024). On 27 April, a heavy downpour in Qardho and its seasonal river catchments triggered widespread flooding in Qardho City, which has a population of 120,000 people. Since 1990, the main historical floods in Puntland, particularly in the Qardo district, have occurred in 1993, 2001, 2018, and 2020. The Qardo floods of 2020 affected 48,000 Households, killed eight people, destroyed 750 houses, damaged four boreholes, and washed away road infrastructure, farms, and other natural resources. The feeder roads connecting villages and settlements, as well as businesses, schools, markets, and offices, are affected by the floods. (International Federation of Red Cross and Red Crescent Societies [IFRC], 2020).

Although the Qardho local government made an effort to deploy various awareness-raising strategies, including posting billboards in the town centre, holding meetings with prominent individuals and the general public, and installing radios in cars, it appears that these measures were insufficient. The key informant interview highlighted that the response to the Qardho floods situation experienced delays attributed to various levels of verification regarding the number of individuals requesting assistance. A significant loss of livelihood occurred as a result of the tardiness in preparing for evacuation and responding to the situation.

The report produced by the IFRC (2020) highlights challenges such as delays in assistance due to verification processes, which result in significant livelihood losses. What if the federal government were interested in stepping in and assisting with the verification process as well? How much time did it take? Undoubtedly, empowering local governments to oversee and manage services proves to be far more effective, practical, and impactful than interventions orchestrated by a centralised authority. Consequently, it is imperative to entrust local governments with the responsibility of administering local services, ensuring administrative devolution, and granting them financial autonomy to manage their allocations and engage with donor or external funding mechanisms.

4.6. Key Challenges Identified

The findings of this study found that the 2014 DRM policy lacks a well-defined framework for community-based disaster risk reduction and management. It also does not encourage the decen-

tralisation of DRM, which is essential for enhancing mitigation and response efforts at the district level.

Furthermore, the study highlights several challenges faced by the policy, including limited financial resources, low awareness among stakeholders, and insufficient engagement from relevant actors. Equally, the Puntland Five-Year Development Plan - 4th Version (2020-2024) indicates that skilled and experienced staff is scarce in DRM at all levels of government and recognises this as a significant constraint. This limitation, coupled with inadequate infrastructure and the absence of information systems, such as early warning systems, hampers disaster preparedness and response. According to UNDRR (2019), SMS-based disaster alerts, as used in Indonesia's early warning systems, can improve local preparedness. Similarly, another best practice is to use local radios, as Ethiopia has successfully utilised radio programmes to educate rural communities about disaster preparedness (Ikram et al., 2020). Awareness is one of the first steps for actors to participate in DRM (Hermansson, 2019; Muriuki et al., 2022; Tao et al., 2023). This can be achieved through the introduction of billboards, television, radio, and leaflets, as well as the formation of environmental awareness groups that would engage residents on the need to adopt DRM (Olawuni, Olowoporoku, & Daramola, 2021).

Additionally, the lack of dedicated financial resources for disaster management further weakens Puntland's ability to address disaster risks effectively, as does the Somalia National Disaster Risk Management Policy. (2020) outlines the challenges faced in disaster risk management in Somalia, including limited workforce, technological and financial resources, and weak coordination mechanisms across various levels of government. Furthermore, the study highlights that the policy does not fully encompass all essential pillars of DRM, including effective mechanisms for monitoring and evaluation, resulting in gaps in prevention and preparedness efforts.

The aforementioned analyses support the argument presented by scholars, including Ikram et al. (2020) that developing countries need DRM to be a primary component of their governance structure.

5. Conclusions

The study concludes that Puntland's 2014 DRM policy functions merely as a document with narrowly and ill-defined provisions, due to whether at the local or national level, as in many cases, each government institution addresses disaster response separately, with limited resources while communities are not fully engaged, and policies may be influenced by the priorities of funders, such as NGOs or external sponsors, rather than reflecting the will of the government.

Ministry of Humanitarian Affairs and Disaster Management of State of Puntland to update the 2014 DRM policy to reflect global standards, i.e. Sendai Framework and Somalia's 2020 DRM Policy, in order to reflect the government's approach to DRM and remain proactive, holistic, and capable of addressing current and emerging disaster risks, with a clear roadmap for achieving the intended outcome.

The redistributive policy should ensure that institutional frameworks, roles, and responsibilities are clearly defined, streamlined, and aligned with the governance system at the state and local levels to enhance the coordination mechanism. For effective policy implementation, government officials and local communities should be capacitated through investment in short courses and training to produce trained trainers, as well as Executive Master's programs in professional studies in emergency and disaster management to handle disasters. In addition, the proposed structures, particularly the Puntland Disaster Management Council (PDMC) and all other Disaster Management structures, including the Puntland Emergency Centre and ministerial focal points, are operationalised and adequately funded. Adopting such an approach strengthens community involvement in policy implementation. It will foster grassroots engagement and localised disaster risk reduction efforts and enhance key pillars of disaster risk management, including but not limited to assessment and research undertakings, resilience building, preparedness, and community engagement.

For sustainable financing, the government is required to establish and operationalise Puntland and District DRM Funds with legal mandates, including mechanisms for community and private sector contribution. This is achieved through transparent budget allocation at the state and local government levels, as well as solicitation of funding support from development agencies and financial partners, accompanied by a detailed implementation plan annexed, including a cash project and budget breakdown. Additionally, the government of Puntland's redistributive DRM policy should explicitly adopt principles from international agreements and align its objectives with global targets, including those of the Sendai Framework and the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), particularly Goal 13 (Climate Action), as well as the disaster management frameworks of the Federal Republic of Somalia.

Furthermore, to enhance the effectiveness of policy formulation and decision-making, the government should establish a specialised unit for public policy review within the State House tasked with evaluating policy proposals submitted by ministries before they are presented to the Cabinet of Ministers for approval. This unit would ensure that the policy proposal aligns with established policy standards and national priorities. In cases where a proposal does not meet the required criteria, the unit would provide recommendations for improvement and return it to the respective ministry for revision, fostering a more rigorous and accountable policy development process.

As usual, the policy is often subject to continuous review and regular updates to reflect emerging challenges, particularly those related to climate change and urbanisation. Hence, the government should develop performance metrics and early warning systems tailored to Puntland's hazard profile.

Lastly, not least, the findings of this study can be generalised to other public policies of the State of Puntland, other Federal Member States, and/or the Federal Republic of Somalia, as community consultations are often undermined during policy formulation or when providing feedback about the outcome of policy implementation.

Acknowledgements: I, the author, express my sincere gratitude to VNG International, which, through the Danwadaag Programme, engaged me as a DRM policy review expert via the Institute of Studies, Researchers, and Academic Community (ISRAAC). During the consultation workshops held in Garowe and Qardho, where focus group discussions (FGDs) and key informant interviews (KIIs) were conducted to gather data, I identified notable shortcomings in the 2014 DRM policy. This inspired me to undertake an academic review of the policy. Through an in-depth analysis of the document, I developed targeted questions that aimed to generate reliable information and meaningful insights.

Conflicts of Interest: The author declares no conflict of interest.

References

1. Ainuddin, S., Routray, J. K., & Ainuddin, S. (2013). People's perception and community participation in disaster risk management: A case study of district Tharparkar, Pakistan. *International Journal of Disaster Risk Reduction*, 5, 165–175. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijdr.2013.10.006>
2. Atta-ur-Rahman, & Khan, A. N. (2011). Analysis of flood causes and associated socio-economic damages in the Hindukush region. *Natural Hazards*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11069-011-9830-8>
3. Balanggoy, H. K. (2024). Implementation of disaster risk reduction and management. Benguet State University, College of Nursing. <https://doi.org/10.18485/ijdrm.2024.6.2.8>
4. Cvetković, V. M., Lipovac, M., Renner, R., Stanarević, S., & Raonić, Z. (2025). A Predictive Framework for Understanding Multidimensional Security Perceptions Among Students in Serbia: The Role of Institutional, Socio-Economic, and Demographic Determinants of Sustainability. *Sustainability*, 17(11), 5030. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su17115030>
5. Cvetković, V. M., Tanasić, J., Ocal, A., Kešetović, Ž., Nikolić, N., & Dragašević, A. (2021). Capacity Development of Local Self-Governments for Disaster Risk Management. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 18(19). doi:10.3390/ijerph181910406

6. Đorđević, I., & Gačić, J. (2024). Sustainable recovery: The link between development and response to disasters. *International Journal of Disaster Risk Management*, 6(2), 223–243. <https://doi.org/10.18485/ijdrm.2024.6.2.15>
7. Ethiopian Disaster Risk Management Commission (EDRMC). (2022). National DRM progress report. Government of Ethiopia.
8. Federal Government of Somalia. (2020). National Disaster Risk Management Policy. Ministry of Humanitarian Affairs & Disaster Management.
9. Garschagen, M. (2016). Decentralising urban disaster risk management in a context of transformation: City-level risk governance in Vietnam. *Habitat International*, 52, 43–49. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.habitatint.2015.08.023>
10. Gautam, D. K., & Phaiju, A. G. (2013). Community-Based Approach to Flood Early Warning in the West Rapti River Basin of Nepal. <https://doi.org/10.5595/idrim.2013.0060>
11. Government of Puntland. (2023). Law No. 3 of 2023 on regions and local governments. Puntland Ministry of Interior, Federal Affairs and Democratization.
12. Greice, L., Kuehlkamp, V. M., Erdmann, A. L., & de Andrade, S. R. (2014). Analysis of public policies: A narrative review.
13. Hermansson, H. (2019). Challenges to community engagement in risk governance. *Journal of Risk Research*, 22(10), 1247–1262. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13669877.2018.1485175>
14. Ikram, S., Elahi, N., Alam, A., Dawar, S., & Dogar, A. A. (2020). Institutional arrangement for disaster risk management: Evidence from Pakistan. *International Journal of Disaster Risk Reduction*. <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2212420920312863>
15. International Federation of Red Cross and Red Crescent Societies (IFRC). (2020, December 18). Somalia: Floods in Qardho – Final Report, DREF Operation No. MDRSO009. ReliefWeb.
16. Ji, H., & Lee, D. (2021). Disaster risk reduction, community resilience, and policy effectiveness: The case of the Hazard Mitigation Grant Program in the United States. *Disasters*, 45(2), 378–402.
17. Joerin, J., Shaw, R., Takeuchi, Y., & Krishnamurthy, R. (2012). Assessing community resilience to climate-related disasters in Chennai, India. *International Journal of Disaster Risk Reduction*, 1, 44–57.
18. Juma, T. O. (2015). The challenges of public policy formulation and evaluation through the questions “what, who, how, and when?” *International Journal of Economics, Commerce and Management*, 3(11).
19. Kafle, K. (2018). Strengthening community-based disaster management: The role of local governments. *International Journal of Disaster Preparedness*, 7(2), 34–48.
20. Kellenberg, D. K., & Mobarak, A. M. (2008). Does rising income increase or decrease damage risk from natural disasters? *Journal of Urban Economics*, 63(3), 788–802.
21. Leka, S., & Jain, A. (2014). Health impact of psychosocial hazards at work: An overview. World Health Organization Discussion Paper. <https://apps.who.int/iris/handle/10665/44428>
22. Milošević, G., Cvjetković-Ivetić, C., & Baturan, L. (2024). State aid for the reconstruction of natural disaster consequences using the Republic of Serbia’s budget funds. *International Journal of Disaster Risk Management*, 6(2), 169–182. <https://doi.org/10.18485/ijdrm.2024.6.2.11>
23. Ministry of Planning, Economic Development and International Cooperation (MoPIC). (2020). Puntland Five-Year Development Plan (4th Version 2020–2024). Puntland State of Somalia.
24. Munene, M., Owuor, S., & Mbatia, P. (2016). Community-driven disaster risk reduction: A case study of urban slums in Nairobi. *Journal of Risk Research*, 19(2), 255–272. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13669877.2014.961517>
25. Muriuki, M., Kimani, M., & Kihoro, J. M. (2022). Building disaster risk awareness through participatory approaches: Evidence from Kenya. *International Journal of Disaster Risk Reduction*, 68, 102705. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijdr.2021.102705>

26. Olawuni, P. O., Olowoporoku, O. A., & Daramola, O. P. (2021). Determinants of residents' participation in disaster risk management in Lagos Metropolis, Nigeria. *International Journal of Disaster Risk Management*.
27. Raikes, J., Smith, K., Jacob, C., & Malcom, J. (2019). Risk communication and community engagement: A review of the Sendai Framework's implementation. *Disaster Prevention and Management*, 28(4), 473–484. <https://doi.org/10.1108/DPM-04-2019-0115>
28. Ricardo, C. A., Pedro, J. A., & Lucas, E. (2024). The effectiveness of disaster risk management policies in Brazilian municipalities. Catholic University of Brasília & Institute for Applied Economic Research (Ipea). https://www.anpec.org.br/encontro/2024/submissao/files_I/i10-3dcf8716447f0503af8e5a51ec1e7130.pdf
29. Rumbach, A. (2015). Decentralization and disaster risk reduction in urban India: Local politics and hazard mitigation in slums. *Habitat International*, 50, 21–28. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.habitatint.2015.08.021>
30. Sant'Anna, A. A. (2018). Not so natural: Unequal effects of public policies on the occurrence of disasters. *Ecological Economics*, 152, 273–281.
31. Scott, Z., & Tarazona, M. (2011). The role of local institutions in building resilience to climate change. Overseas Development Institute (ODI). <https://cdn.odi.org/media/documents/7072.pdf>
32. Serafim, M., & Dias, R. B. (2012). Análise de política: uma revisão da literatura. *Cadernos Gestão Social*. <https://docs.bvsalud.org/biblioref/2016/07/625/36885-151112-1-pb.pdf>
33. Smith, A. B., & Matthews, J. L. (2015). Quantifying uncertainty and variable sensitivity within the US billion-dollar weather and climate disaster cost estimates. *Natural Hazards*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11069-015-1678-x>
34. Somalia Institute for Development and Research Analysis (SIDRA). (2020). Community survey and mapping for district disaster risk management. <https://sidrainstitute.org/wp-content/uploads/2020/04/Disaster-Risk-Management-Study-Report.pdf>
35. Suriyanto, S., Alim, S., Nindrea, R. D., & Trisnantoro, L. (2019). Regional policy for disaster risk management in developing countries within the Sendai Framework: A systematic review. *Open Access Macedonian Journal of Medical Sciences*, 7(21), 3623–3628. <https://doi.org/10.3889/oamjms.2019.614>
36. Tao, W., Liu, Y., & Xu, D. (2023). Enhancing disaster preparedness through localized education programs: A Chinese case study. *International Journal of Disaster Risk Science*, 14(1), 34–48. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13753-023-00400-9>
37. The Office for the Coordination of Humanitarian Affairs. (2004). Tsunami compounds an already serious humanitarian situation in Somalia. United Nations OCHA. <https://www.unocha.org/publications/report/somalia/tsunami-compounds-already-serious-humanitarian-situation-somalia-says-un>
38. UNDP. (2022). Disaster risk assessment paper – Bureau for Crisis Prevention and Recovery. United Nations Development Programme.
39. UNISDR. (2009). Terminology on disaster risk reduction. United Nations International Strategy for Disaster Reduction. <https://www.undrr.org/publication/2009-unisdr-terminology-disaster-risk-reduction>.

